

Right trapezium with one function and a special 5-gon

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1 Local extrema at right trapezium

We turn to the trapezium in the following figure:

With the elementary area formula we obtain for this trapezium:

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (x_p + x) \cdot (y - y_p)$$

Derivation:

$$F' = \frac{1}{2} \cdot ((x_p + x) \cdot y' + y - y_p)$$

Using of the necessary condition $F' = 0$:

$$y_p - y = y' \cdot (x_p + x)$$

Now we calculate the perimeter:

$$U = x_p + x + y - y_p + \sqrt{(x - x_p)^2 + (y - y_p)^2}$$

with the chain rule:

$$U' = 1 + y' + \frac{x - x_p + (y - y_p) \cdot y'}{\sqrt{(x - x_p)^2 + (y - y_p)^2}}$$

With $U' = 0$ it follows:

$$\frac{x_p - x + (y_p - y) \cdot y'}{\sqrt{(x - x_p)^2 + (y - y_p)^2}} = 1 + y'$$

To a right triangle with $x_p = 0$ we get for the area:

$$y_p - y = xy'$$

to the perimeter:

$$\frac{(y_p - y) \cdot y' - x}{\sqrt{x^2 + (y - y_p)^2}} = 1 + y'$$

We look at the rectangle in the following figure:

To the area we get:

$$F = (y - y_p) \cdot x \quad F' = y - y_p + xy'$$

with the necessary condition $F' = 0$:

$$xy' = y_p - y$$

extremum perimeter:

$$U = 2x + 2 \cdot (y - y_p) \quad U' = 2 + 2y'$$

With the necessary condition $U' = 0$ it follows:

$$y' = -1$$

2 Local extrema at a special 5-gon

Now we turn our attention to the 5-gon in the figure: (x_p, y_p) are invariant.)

The 5-gon is composed with a trapezium and a isosceles triangle. Because of this we obtain for the area:

$$F = (x_p + x) \cdot (y_p - y) + (y - f(0)) \cdot x$$

Derivative:

$$F' = y_p - y - (x_p + x) \cdot y' + xy' + y - f(0)$$

If we use the necessary condition $F' = 0$ of local extrumum, we get:

$$y_p = x_p y' + f(0)$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder, "Special extreme value problems and extremum principles",
Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002